

INVESTIGATING THE ALGERIAN SECONDARY EDUCATION TEACHERS' ROLE AS RESEARCHERS: AIN MERANE DISTRICT/CHLEF AS A CASE STUDY*

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Abstract

Research has been considered as a continuous process among EFL practitioners for better knowledge stock about the field and performances. Consequently, teacher as a researcher in the secondary education is the core concern of this investigation. This journey aims at exploring teachers' initiative to embark on research at the secondary education sector. This study is concerned with highlighting the present state of Continuous research process among teachers taking into consideration both opportunities offered by the Ministry of National Education and teacher's initiative for research, via the lens of English as Foreign Language teachers career. The investigation targets problematic areas related to the aforementioned issues as; motivation, Detriments, research engagement and teachers' perception of research in their fieldwork and interest. To attain this objective, the researchers opted for the use of a mixed-methods approach namely; delivering a questionnaire to twenty [20] teachers from three different secondary schools in Ain Merane district/Chlef. Then, the inspector of English at this district was also interviewed. Findings revealed a wide gap between the research perspective and its ongoing in the secondary education sector, due to detriments as; absence of support by the administration. Yet, teachers' total absence in doing research is a consequence of time detriment. The need for a more responsive and inclusive room for a serious research framework is underscored by the current study. Ultimately, ensuring high-quality in the educational process and its adaptability to promoting landscapes in the sector of education can be realized through backing up teachers' professional development.

Key words: *Research gap, Teacher as researcher, Teachers' Professional Development, Algerian secondary education sector, English as a foreign language.*

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1. Introduction

Embarking on a research at the secondary education can help refining the existing skills for teachers and it aims at exploring innovative approaches for the field of their interest. This step is part of the process of promoting teachers' Continuous Professional Development (CPD) in the Algerian secondary education sector. To attain this objective, secondary school teachers both experienced and novice ones are required for their initiative to embark on research. The point is that teacher's role as a researcher is indispensable for his professional advance. By doing research, a teacher can be able to address his shortcomings in his daily classroom performances as well as his skills gaps.

Moreover, doing research empowers EFL teachers' adaptation to educational changes by being agents of change. This quality helps teachers face challenges related to the field of their concern. At the same time, carrying out research ensures high quality of teaching and learning. Consequently, this research investigates secondary school teachers' continuity to do research as an in-service process. It also explores the possible existence of room offered for an overall existence of voluntary research process within the educational landscape, outside all sorts of trainings and recycling programs administered by the ministry of national education in Algeria. This investigation focuses much on teachers' attitudes toward research without neglecting their motivation to be researchers. The current investigation aims at promoting a research-oriented culture among secondary school teachers of English for enhancing their continuous professional development.

To satisfy the aforementioned query and attain its goals, the following research questions are formulated;

1. How do teachers perceive research at the Algerian secondary education sector?

2. Do teachers carry out research at the secondary education field?

3. What challenges do teachers face to do research at the secondary education?

As plausible answers for the previously stated questions, the following hypotheses are formulated;

1. Teachers at the secondary education sector are reluctant to do research.

2. Secondary education teachers do not carry out any research process.

3. Time constraints and administration negligence hinder research at the secondary education.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. Definition of Continuous Professional Development

The quality of Continuous Professional Development has been defined differently by many scholars, as far as (Friedman, Davis, & Phillips, 2000) are concerned. According to them, (CPD) is a perspective that emphasizes individuals' expertise, competences and skills for better performances in their fieldwork. In the educational setting, CPD aims at satisfying teachers' workplace demands concerning what and how to teach. Apart from that, CPD is much concerned with improving and updating teachers' knowledge background about their professional requirements in

terms of classroom management and problem-solving. But, this definition is still aborted when compared to that by Little (1993), who stated that professional development emphasizes enhancing in-service teachers as practitioners in the educational field. But, the quality cannot be restricted to a certain period.

Most importantly, (Schlager & Fusco, 2003) dealt with this notion as: “A *career-long, context-specific, continuous endeavor that is guided by standards, grounded in the teacher's own work. It is a collaborative effort, in which teachers receive support from peer networks, local administration, teacher educators, and outside experts.*” (Schlager & Fusco, 2003, p. 5).

The above quote provides us with a more accurate definition of teachers' continuous professional development as part of their ongoing career growth. In-service trainings that are carried out by teachers are also a long-term research process that aims at updating teachers' competencies for better daily school performances.

2.2. Research as an Advantageous Process

Doing research helps educators deepen their expertise about their field work. It also allows them gain a wide understanding of their field requirements in terms of knowledge and engaging techniques of managing their job to improve learners' success. Equipping teachers with the necessary qualifications in the form of pedagogical knowledge for detecting their classroom challenges and face them by seeking right and effective solutions. Moreover, a teacher researcher gains tenets and skills to bridge the gap between theory and practice in his fieldwork, as far as classroom management and evaluation are concerned. Critical thinking development is another advantage for doing research, as teachers are meant to reflect on their knowledge and classroom practices for developing their skills for better achievements.

It is remarkable to point out to (Kaiser and König, 2019, p. 32), who identified the main components of teacher professional competence namely; First, knowledge which refers to teachers' mastery of their job in their field work context. On the basis of this quality, teachers are meant to judge and decide about their classroom setting. This dimension concerns what and how to do things as being well-versed in their subject of teaching and possessing the necessary tools of delivering knowledge to learners. Second, there are dispositions which rotate around teachers' availability and their readiness to engage in an effective teaching learning process. Then, we have strategies that are about procedures and ways for attaining certain goals.

According to (Yuan and Yang, 2020), the so-called classroom-based research, or case studies, teachers act on their daily performances by reflecting on their teaching process. This process can enable teachers enhance their critical thinking and problem-solving skills, for taking pedagogical decisions in reference to theoretical foundations at advancement in all aspects of the teaching/learning process. Then, act on their professional characteristics and qualifications to offer more room for more learning opportunities. These procedures are all the vain seek of upgrading and advancing teachers' professional practices. These steps end in promoting teachers-learners' outcomes within the teaching/learning process. The following figure displays components of teachers' professional competence and their correlation.

Adapted from Kunter et al. (2013)

Figure 1. Theoretical framework on teacher competence development

2.2.1. Teachers' Collaboration within schools

In the secondary education sector precisely, teachers are meant to carry out some sorts of collaborations. These procedures can be in the form of attendance of tutorial for peer teaching and lessons planning. In addition to that, they discuss the implementation of certain teaching/learning strategies, as well as the challenges they face in their daily practices. Their debate is also open to periodical collaboration. This idea was claimed by (Miquel, and Duran, 2017).

While implementing the self-organized professional collaboration, teachers need to schedule their meeting opportunities and time allocation for that process. Moreover, they were in need for fixing the issues they are meant to deal with. So, a scope of collaboration planning is needed for every collaboration or research opportunity for teachers in the field of their interest. The point is that this can be considered as part of their collaboration for research project implementation, (Jurkowski, Ulrich, and Müller, 2020).

2.2.2. Research Competence

Teachers' success in equipping learners with the necessary tools to adapt to the requirement and challenges of social and workplace difficulties, they are gain these skills and competencies through being researchers. This continuous quality required teacher to carry on research for acquiring the most recent and practical skills related to their professional life. Therefore, an inquiry-oriented approach is required for its integration as an in-service process or known as (a research-based teacher education) process (Belasić & Meserko, 2020).

2.2.3. Research-Based Teaching

Research-based teaching is considered as a crucial process for teachers' professional growth. This quality enhances teachers' classroom performances. So, research-based teaching equips teachers with the necessary or the most recent skills about their field of interest, and it enables them to face challenges in their work life by empowering their expertise and enriching it with the most effective and practicable strategies for a better ongoing of the classroom management. This

procedure can promote an effective collaboration among colleagues by finding solutions and sharing them.

According to (Böttcher-Oschmann et al. 2021), research competence implies conducting research as a reflection process and evidence use for problem-solving situations in the classroom environment. The implication is that this process is not a real engagement in research with its steps and procedures. This case can result in lack of research competence practice as a real gap. Then, the reflective character is a quality gained and maintained throughout the teaching experience. The latter is of a standard duration when it is about five year or more as claimed by Gore et al. (2023), when stating that the typical length of teaching experience is five years classroom management and performance.

Ziani & Lahma (2020, p. 95) pointed out that teachers are required to be taught how to take responsibility of their continuing professional development in the period of their in-service training. The action can be realized through focusing on developing a reflective character and embarking on research.

La Velle (2024) emphasized the importance of research as an in-service quality among teachers by giving much importance to their reflection on their daily teaching when stating that: *“One of the most important principles in educating to teach is the notion that teachers are also researchers of their own practice. The pedagogic cycle of understanding -> preparing -> instructing -> assessing -> reflecting, is, as we have long argued”* (La Velle, 2024, p. 2). The scholar has identified five stages for the research process namely; Understanding the teaching content and being well-versed in the subject. The second phase is about the preparation of the teaching content that should be tallied according to learners’ level. Then, there is the instructing step that is an embodiment of the teaching daily practices. Next, we have assessment of the teaching learning performances. The last step is reflecting on what has been done by changing or adapting what has not been efficient or effective. Phases of an action research process are summarized by (Urszula Ostrowska, 2025, p. 7) in the following figure. What attract our intention in the figure bellow are teachers’ continuous reflective procedures in their teaching process as part of action research.

One can deduce from the previous quote that teachers need to possess that reflective character which enables them act on their classroom daily practices with reference to research as a basis for any change in their performances. At his stage teachers are meant to be disciples and supervisors of their own as they acquire new knowledge and become reference for others.

Figure 2. Phases of action research (Urszula Ostrowska, 2025)

2.3. Significance of in-service research

Magnaye (2022) identified an important correlation between teachers' competence that is related to pedagogy as far as classroom management and evaluation is concerned and research competence development. It can be said that promoting research competence requires enhancing research practical skills and applying knowledge in real life contexts. At this stage, teachers are expected to work on upgrading their skills in terms of knowledge and how to manage their classrooms.

The in-service research is about teachers' professional development in terms of their skills and knowledge. It can be in the form of tutorials, workshops or other types of collaboration between teachers from different schools. In-service research enables teachers keep themselves up-dated with the most recent pedagogical and technological advancements. It can also enhance teachers' critical thinking and better classroom management. Moreover, in service-research helps teachers address their learners' needs and assess them. Syllabus refinement, textbooks evaluation and testing the validity of the teaching practices are also procedures that can be carried out for innovation introduction.

According to Lansari & Bouabdallah (2022, pp. 91-98), teachers' training is an indispensable process since 2008. The idea is that teachers are expected to go on trainings even before being certified with full responsibilities. The necessity for continuity in research and more precisely in the in-service stage for teachers is justified by the following statement: "*the personal and long-term professional needs of the teacher are legitimated*" (Day, 1999, p. 40). One can deduce from this statement that teaching is a continuous developing process to face challenges and adapting to the unexpected situations in this domain. An example is technology, new methods and other participants in the teaching/learning process. Another point is that was highlighted by (Njenga, 2022) stating that research deals with the breaking down of monotonous learning, stress and boredom by focusing on skills for professional concerns.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The methodological framework of the current investigation makes use of a mixed-methods approach, synthesizing qualitative and quantitative paradigms to examine the state of teachers as researchers in the secondary education sector.

3.2. Data Collection and Sampling

3.2.1. Numerical Data [Questionnaire]

The numerical data collection comprises the use of a questionnaire that is about both open and close-ended questions to elicit data from twenty-two secondary school teachers at the district of Ain Merane at the Department of Chlef in Algeria. These teachers represent the English language practitioners in the field of teaching.

Moreover, the nature of the research as a case study determines the size of the sample. Selection of this limited population can be justified by emphasis on holding much control over the participants. Another reason is the nature of the educational process and its circumstances as a one-fits-all system in the Algerian secondary schools. The idea goes for the inspector too, as he represents a common example of all inspectors in the Algerian departments by being submitted to the Ministry of National Education instructions.

3.2.2. Qualitative Data [Interview]

At this stage a semi-structured interview was conducted with the general inspector of English in charge of the department of Chlef. The latter represents the most reliable source of information about teachers' performances in the district of Ain Merane. Apart from that, he is the closest person to the Academy of Chlef as the most knowledgeable one about teaching.

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative framework examines teachers' awareness of the research process its frequency distributions throughout their teaching career, consequently, implementing statistical analysis of the collected data through the implementation of the questionnaire option.

4.2. Qualitative Analysis

Qualitative analysis implements thematic coding of interview and attitudinal data, examination of the recurring patterns of research at the secondary education sector. The matter implies figuring out perceptions.

5. Results

This step is devoted for highlighting data collected by using research tools namely; teachers' questionnaire and interview with the inspector.

5.1. Questionnaire Results

The followings are data collected through handing a questionnaire to secondary education teachers at the district of Ain Merane in Chlef.

a. Gender

Figure 3. Teachers' Gender

The above pie-chart displays gender distribution of the participants in this research process. Henceforth, one can deduce that the very majority of teachers at Ain Merane district are females. Very few teachers are males. Feminization of the teaching staff is due to females' interest in the educational sector.

b. Teaching Experience

Concerning the teachers' experience, one can state that most if not all teachers (95 %) are of more than 10 years in the field of teaching. This case paves the way for their ability to embark on research about the field of their interest.

c. Teachers' perception of Continuous Professional Development

Figure 4. Teachers' perception of CPD

According the above graph, it is apparent that there is a full agreement among teachers' on CPD as an ongoing indispensable process. The point is that all teachers admit that CPD is needed even in their in-service period.

d. In-service engagement in research

Figure 5. Teachers' in-service Engagement in Research

When coming to teachers' engagement in in-service research, most respondents said that they were not given any chance to carry on an investigation process. Only one of them said that he carried on a research process during his in-service training.

e. Encouragement of Research among Teachers

Figure 6. Encouragement of Research among Teachers

According to the above bar graph, the very majority of participants i.e. (19) of them responded negatively to encouragements provided by educational institutions to promote research among secondary school teachers'. Only one of the teachers admitted a rare implementation of this procedure. One can say that the reason behind this massive absence of research in the secondary education sector is the total neglect of encouragement of teachers to be researchers by educational institutions in their own field. Another point of a paramount importance about this matter is the training opportunities offered by the Ministry of National Education namely; Seminars and recycling procedures as; coordination among teachers in the same school, and online lessons posted by peers for the teaching community.

f. Formal research Activities for CPD

Figure 7. Formal research Activities for CPD

According to the above bar-graph, the very majority of respondents reckoned attendance of seminars. This option is held in a chosen school as part of teachers' CPD. It is organized by the inspector once or twice a year depending on any novelties about the field. Whereas; conferences, workshops and action research process is of a very rare occurrence among teachers, as only one of them admitted being involved in.

5.2. Interview Data

At this stage, it is worth stating that the interview option is meant to be limited to collection of qualitative data contrary to the questionnaire that was concerned with collecting different data.

Question One: How do you perceive research in the secondary education sector?

The inspector's response implied a paramount importance and necessity of doing research for knowledge and skills enhancing among teachers in the secondary education sector. But, he added saying that there is a total absence of teacher as a researcher quality, as no signs of research occur in the secondary education.

Question Two: How do you see research importance for teachers' Continuous Professional Development?

The respondent emphasized research effectiveness in upgrading teachers' skills about how and what to teach. He also insisted on the vital role of doing research in updating teachers' knowledge about their field of work and raising their awareness about the most recent advancements.

Question Three: Apart from research, what type of professional development activities are set for secondary teachers in your district?

The interviewee answered by mentioning only seminars as the sole CPD opportunities for teachers at the secondary education. What is worth mentioning here is the inspector's body language before answering by shaking his head and loosening his lips indicating an unsatisfactory state.

Question Four: Do you think seminars are sufficient for teachers' Continuous Understanding Development?

The inspector's response implies a wide gap in the CPD pedagogy and training activities. The implication is that seminars are held by inspectors once a year in a very limited time that does not allow deeper analysis of educational constraints, or giving room for teachers to do research.

Question Five: Are there any research initiatives by teachers?

The inspector admitted a total absence of teachers' initiative to do research in the secondary education field.

Question Six: Are teachers encouraged to undertake research by educational institutions?

The interviewee's negative answer and facial expressions indicate a total absence of encouragement to do research by any of the official institutions in the department of Chlef as a whole. He added justifying his concern of absence of his encouragement for teachers by stating his subjection to the Ministry of National Education instructions. He said that he is concerned more with formal training by applying educators' instruction.

6. Discussion of Findings

Findings of the current study align with the hypothesis that there is an absence of research among teachers at the secondary education sector. The only opportunities set as part of teachers' CPD. are seminars and coordination session at schools. The case does not adhere to what (Schlager & Fusco, 2003) stated about CPD. as a quality throughout teachers' career, that should be concerned with what really goes in their vivid practices at schools and collaboration with other specialists. This state indicates a wide gap between teachers' perspectives about their continuous research process as part of their schemata and their real practices. This phenomenon is a consequence of many monitoring factors. The first one is related to institutional factors as lack of sponsoring or funding with limited financial resources that lead to an avoidance behavior of research. In other words; this neglect leads to an automatic de-motivation of teachers to engage in research activities.

The second factor behind absence of research among secondary education teachers is time detriment. The reason is that teachers are dealing with an overloaded timetable which does not give room for being researchers. Another reason is the nature of seminars as domineering collaborative and cooperative procedures contrary to research process and workshops as being passive and individual ones. Lack of resources is another factor inhibiting teachers from reengaging in research in their field work. Nevertheless, teachers showed positive attitudes towards conducting research a process if motivated by bonus either financial or a promotion.

Another point worth mentioning is respondents' agreement [both teachers and the inspector] on the importance of research. The interviewee provided complementary insights about research and its importance for secondary school teachers. The idea can be justified by their awareness that research is the most reliable and effective way to meet their learners' needs and facilitate the teaching/learning process in the school setting. The implication behind magnifying conducting research implies introducing innovation and making of the teacher an agent of change regarding his skills and teaching methods. Another point is that concerns teachers' belief in research as a means of personal growth and career advancement. Teachers also manifested a great point that concerns the possibility of pursuing studies if given a chance that helps them being inhabited and involved in doing research.

Moreover, findings indicate a potential lack of encouragement to engage in doing educational research among the very majority of teachers that reinforces the challenges faced in the secondary education sector.

7. Recommendations

Serious measures should be taken to electrify teachers' willingness to delve in research in their field of work. First, the educational authorities are urged for future renovations and fostering a culture of research among secondary school educators. The matter concerns establishing official libraries that should be concerned with providing the necessary knowledge stock for teachers to conduct research and upgrading their aptitudes. It is also highly recommended to unfold and foster

networking opportunities within the teaching community and experts in their field to do research.

Another procedure is the establishment of collaborative projects and partnership with universities to ease teachers' access to academic support and resources. As an efficient procedure, we can refer to providing workshops and trainings which should be tailored by university teachers or foreign collaborators as the British Council like Teachers' Knowledge Test [TKT].

8. Conclusion

The current study tried to offer valuable and comprehensive insights and facts about research in the secondary education sector. Throughout this journey, there was much focus on the examination of teachers' attitudes, aptitudes and their initiatives to do research. There was also emphasis on the main detriments standing against teacher's continuous character as a researcher in the Algerian secondary education. It is worth stating that the investigation of teacher's character as a researcher in Algerian secondary education came out with a significant imbalance between the Ministry of Education perspectives about teachers' recycling opportunities, and the real ongoing of educators' achievements and shortfalls increase within the secondary education community.

This investigation underscores the importance of research achievements and practices. It becomes evident that engagement in research faces different detriments and issues namely; lack of resources, educational and administrative constraints. Moreover, the secondary education environment does not provide any minimum support for teachers' independent research initiatives. The matter concerns most the integration of a (research-based teacher education) process as advised by (Belasić & Meserko, 2020). The research highlights several key findings that have confirmed the formulated hypotheses by the researcher. There is a clear dissatisfaction with the current rare research opportunities for teachers' CPD programs. Thus, teachers are caused to be reluctant to embark on any possible self-directed initiatives to do research in the secondary education.

Finally, one can state that this investigation aims at digging deeper in the teaching community's vivid practices. Moreover, this research seeks great contribution to the stock of knowledge. This contribution comprises analyzing phenomena for their understanding and offering possible solutions. Upgrading teachers' skills is also another target for this investigation by putting at their disposal tenets to face challenges in their daily school practices for better performances and greater achievements.

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